

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: MEXICO

Tracing Environmental Change Through Time: Human Impacts on the Montebello Karst Lakes

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18420605>

Human impact has become the leading cause of environmental change in lakes, especially in the neotropical aquatic ecosystems of southern Mexico, owing to the rapid human population growth during the 20th century. Historical data for the study area are extremely limited before 2010, and the few existing records are inadequate for reconstructing the baseline conditions of water quality or biodiversity in these tropical freshwater ecosystems. However, the neotropical ecosystems in southern Mexico represent a hotspot for tropical endemic species that could vanish, possibly even before they are described. The Montebello Lake district in southern Mexico is one of those regions with particular importance owing to its tourism appeal and numerous lakes. This lake district, part of the Río Grande de Comitán Basin, is located on the Central Plateau of Chiapas in southeastern Mexico and belongs to the upper Grijalva–Usumacinta River system (Fig. 1).

The Montebello Lake district mainly consists of Mesozoic carbonate rocks, primarily Cretaceous limestones and dolomites, which are highly karstified and interbedded with marls. Sandstones, shales, and volcaniclastics are also present in areas with complex geological structures in the basin. Karst-driven processes have shaped waterscapes characterized by sinkholes, dolines, and extensive underground drainage networks. In the depressions formed by these processes, 139 water bodies comprise the “Lagunas de Montebello” lake system (Alcocer *et al.* 2023).

The hydrology of the system is shaped by detailed interactions between the surface water and groundwater. The soils—mainly Rendzinas and Leptosols—are thin and rich in organic matter, while Luvisols and Vertisols are common in the valleys, supporting

Fig. 1 Geographic setting of the Montebello Lake district within the Grande de Comitán River basin, Chiapas, Mexico (top). Spatial distribution of lakes within the Lagunas de Montebello National Park (bottom). Lakes situated in the lowland plains (green) exhibit anthropogenic impacts and eutrophic conditions, while those in the upland mountain region (blue) retain relatively pristine, oligotrophic characteristics.

agriculture. The humid subtropical to temperate climate, characterized by annual rainfall ranging from 1,200 to 1,800 mm and noticeable seasonality, promotes aquifer recharge that sustains the lakes (Salguero-Olvera, 2018).

Morphologically, lakes are highly diverse, ranging from small shallow bodies to large deep bodies, with water volumes varying by several orders of magnitude (Alcocer *et al.* 2016). Lakes can be divided into two groups based on their location (Figs. 1 and 2). The first group includes lakes on the plateau in the northwestern region, which are mainly fed by groundwater but also receive surface water from the Río Grande de Comitán River. Artificial channels and overflow connect them during the rainy season. The second group consists of lakes at higher altitudes in the southeastern mountains, which are fed almost exclusively by groundwater (Durán Calderón *et al.* 2014). This distinction is essential for understanding the patterns of anthropogenic impact (Alcocer *et al.* 2018). Most human development and activities are focused on the plateau, whereas the mountainous zone remains largely forested and relatively undisturbed by human activity.

The sedimentary record from one of these lakes provides detailed insights into environmental changes during the Late Holocene. Paleolimnological studies have shown a gradual shift toward drier conditions starting approximately 3,400 years ago, linked to shifts in global climate patterns, including changes in the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) and variations in the frequency and severity of decadal events such as the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) (Franco-Gaviria *et al.* 2020). In Mexico, a period of increased drought intensity was identified during the Classic period of Mesoamerican history (100–900 CE) (Rodríguez-Ramírez *et al.* 2015). This drought period is also evident in the Montebello lakes record, which experienced its most severe droughts between 500 and 900 CE (Franco-Gaviria *et al.* 2020). These harsh conditions caused the earliest Maya inhabitants (Tojolabales and Tseltales) to abandon the area between 900 and 1200 CE. The subsequent absence of humans and increased moisture allowed the cleared forests to recover, leading to the resurgence of montane cloud forests, including tropical and temperate species (Arqueología Mexicana, 2022). Contrary to being a static environment, Montebello displays resilience and the ability to recover despite the climatic challenges.

The main causes of these disturbances have shifted over the past few centuries. When people reoccupied the region between 1200 and 1521 CE, they made significant changes to its landscape. This may have included building or expanding canals connecting lakes on the northwestern plain, which altered hydrological connections and water flow (Ceough, 1944; Alcocer *et al.* 2023). Recently, the region has faced new disturbances caused by human activities such as deforestation, agricultural expansion, and urban development.

The most sudden and widespread change occurred during the 20th century, driven by national socioeconomic and political forces. Programs such as the Agrarian Reform (1940s) and, notably, the National Forest Clearance Program (PRONADE, 1972–1983) promoted deforestation for agricultural expansion (March Mifsud and Flamenco Sandoval 1996). Between 1960 and 2000, the area experienced growth in human settlements and the expansion of intensive farming practices. Land-cover analyses show a drastic

shift from mostly forest to a mosaic where cropland and grazing land made up 55% and urban areas 10% by 2025 (Rivera-Herrera *et al.* 2025). This process was further accelerated by the arrival of Guatemalan migrants from Maya groups (Chuj, Cakchikel, and K'anjobal) in the late 1980s and the creation of communities such as Tziscaco in 1983, which added new layers of social complexity and increased pressure on natural resources (CONANP, 2007).

Sediment cores also showed increasing erosion reaching the plateau lakes, caused by deforestation and land use changes (Caballero *et al.* 2019, 2022). This process has been ongoing since the 1950s and is linked to key trophic shifts, with lakes that were oligotrophic rapidly changing to mesotrophic and eutrophic conditions. These shifts occurred during the 1950s in lakes directly affected by sediment transport and agricultural runoff from the Río Grande de Comitán, and later in the 2000s in less connected plateau lakes (Caballero *et al.* 2025). The start of the system's current degradation can be traced back decades, but major shifts in some lakes occurred in the 2000s, as reported by local residents.

Today, the effects of these increasing pressures are evident, caused by various competing stressors such as fertilizer-rich agricultural runoff, urban expansion, and discharges of untreated wastewater, which degrade the water quality (Rodríguez-Izquierdo *et al.* 2023; Mazari-Hiriart *et al.* 2024). Eutrophication, characterized by high nutrient levels, reduced water clarity, phytoplankton blooms, and hypoxic conditions, leading to fish kills, has become the most serious and dangerous threat. Recently, a striking discovery revealed the hidden danger: although local communities reported sudden changes in water color and sulfur smells starting in 2003, retrospective satellite analysis showed that signs of eutrophication, indicated by color change, were already present in 1990 (Rivera-Herrera *et al.* 2025), and paleolimnology confirmed that deterioration has been ongoing since the 1950s.

This 13-year gap between the initial instrumental detection and visible changes shows how degradation can develop quietly before accelerating suddenly. Currently, degradation levels vary but follow a clear impact gradient based on the initial functional divide: lakes on the northwestern plateau, with more human influence, are the most advanced in eutrophication, while lakes in the southeastern mountain range, with less human activity and more forested basins, remain oligotrophic. This trend is concerning and suggests that eutrophication is likely to continue progressing, thereby threatening these relatively pristine lake waters. Paleolimnological data from one of these apparently untouched oligotrophic lakes revealed that it has begun to exhibit signs of eutrophication, and that deforestation and erosion have impacted this ecosystem, leading to a shift in diatom flora from benthic to planktonic dominance (Caballero *et al.* 2025). Furthermore, rising temperatures have also impacted these lakes, favoring smaller planktonic species at the expense of the original, diverse, and sometimes endemic taxa that were previously present in these lakes.

The long history of the “Lagunas de Montebello” demonstrates its resilience to major natural and climatic disturbances. However, the rapid and combined human impacts over the past century pose a fundamentally different threat against which the system lacks natural defenses. This underscores the urgent need for an

Fig. 2 Lakes in upland forested areas, away from significant human activity (e.g., Lake Tziscaco), have largely remained pristine, blue, and oligotrophic. In contrast, lakes in the lowland plains are surrounded by agricultural fields and urban settlements (e.g., Lake Balantitc), receive inputs of human waste, and show impacted, green, eutrophic conditions.

Fig. 3 Schematic representation of plain lakes and mountain lakes, highlighting the different anthropogenic impacts they have experienced over time.

integrated watershed management plan to address both the social and environmental causes of the problem. The sediment record of Montebello offers an important lesson: nature can recover if given a chance to do so. However, this chance now depends on translating scientific insights into coordinated management that views the watershed as a single, interconnected system rather than as separate parts.

References

- Alcocer J., Oseguera L.A., Sánchez G., González C.G., Martínez J.R. & González R. 2016. Bathymetric and morphometric surveys of the Montebello lakes, Chiapas. *Journal of Limnology* 75(s1): 56-65 <https://doi.org/10.4081/jlimnol.2016.1343>
- Alcocer, J.; Merino-Ibarra, M.; Oseguera, L.A.; Escolero, O. 2018. Anthropogenic Impacts on Tropical Karst Lakes: "Lagunas de Montebello," Chiapas. *Ecology*, 11, e2029
- Alcocer, J., Escolero, O. & Álvarez, F. (Eds.). 2023. Las "Lagunas de Montebello". Joyas de la naturaleza amenazadas. Facultad de Estudios Superiores Iztacala, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México. México. 80 pp. ISBN: 9786073073608
- Arqueología Mexicana. 2022. Zona Arqueológica de Chinkultic, Chiapas. *Arqueología Mexicana* 102: 43-45.

Caballero, M., Mora, L., Muñoz, E., Escolero, O., Bonifaz, R., Ruiz, C. & Prado, B. (2019). Anthropogenic influence on the sediment chemistry and diatom assemblages of Balantetik Lake, Chiapas, Mexico. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 7(14):15935-15943. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-019-04581-9>

Caballero, M., Prado, B., Mora, L., Ruiz Fernández, A. C., Muñoz, E., & Sánchez, W. 2022. Paleoenvironmental record from Lake San Lorenzo, Montebello, Chiapas, Mexico. *Revista Internacional de Contaminación Ambiental* 38: 41–47.

Caballero, M., Waters, M.N., Amezcua, M., Ruiz-Fernández, A.C., Sigala, I. & Alcocer, J. 2025. Recent human-induced ecological changes in a Neotropical karst lake of southern Mexico. *Catena* 256: 109119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2025.109119>

Caballero M., Vázquez G., Ruiz-Fernández AC, Alcocer J., Mora-Palomino L. 2025. Diatom diversity and distribution in Neotropical karst lakes under anthropogenic stress. *PlosOne* 20 (7): e0327201. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0327201>

Ceough, R. 1944. The Temple of the Thousand Steps at Agua Azul. A Report on the Archaeological Phenomena at Agua Azul, Chiapas, Mexico; National Institute of Anthropology and History of Mexico.

CONANP (Comisión de Áreas Naturales Protegidas). (2007). Programa de Conservación y Manejo Parque Nacional Lagunas de Montebello, México. Comisión de Áreas Naturales Protegidas, SEMARNAT. México. 194 pp.

Durán Calderón, I.; Escolero Fuentes, O.A.; Muñoz Salinas, E.; Castillo Rodríguez, M.; Silva Romo, G. 2014. Cartografía geomorfológica a escala 1:50000 del Parque Nacional Lagunas de Montebello, Chiapas (México). *Boletín de la Sociedad Geológica de México* 66: 263–277

Franco-Gaviria, F., Correa-Metrio, A., Núñez-Useche, F., Zawisza, E., Caballero, M., Prado, B., Wojewódka, M. & Olivares, G. (2020). Millennial-to-centennial scale lake system development in the mountains of tropical Mexico. *Boreas* 49: 363–374. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12430>

March Mifsut, I.J. and Flamenco Sandoval, A. (1996). Evaluación rápida de la deforestación en las áreas naturales protegidas de Chiapas (1970-1993). El Colegio de la Frontera Sur. San Cristóbal de las Casas, Chiapas. 66 pp.

Mazari-Hiriart, M., Fernández-Reyes, A., Alvarado-Velázquez, J., Gradilla-Hernández M.S. & Díaz-Vázquez, D. (2024). Water quality management in a tropical karstic system influenced by land use in Chiapas, Mexico. *Environmental Challenges* 16: 100981. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2024.100981>

Rivera-Herrera, M., Alcocer, J., Palma-Castro, A., Sánchez-Carrillo, S., García-Oliva, F., Vargas-Sánchez, M., Soria-Reinoso, I. & Oseguera, L.A. 2025. Ecological impacts of land-use and land-cover change in a tropical karst: The Río Grande de Comitán Basin, Mexico (1974–2025). *Earth Systems and Environment* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41748-025-00896-5>

Rodríguez-Izquierdo, R., Alvarado-Velázquez, J., García-Meneses, P.M., Merino-Pérez, L. & Mazari-Hiriart, M. (2023). Inequality, water accessibility, and health impacts in Chiapas, Mexico. *Regional Environmental Challenges* 16: 100981. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-022-01993-1>

Rodríguez-Ramírez A., Caballero M., Roy P., Ortega B., Vázquez-Castro G., Lozano-García S., 2015. Climatic variability and human impact during the last 2000 years in western Mesoamerica: evidences of late Classic (AD 600-900) and Little Ice Age drought events. *Climate of the Past* 11, 1239- 1248 doi: 10.5194/cp-11-1239-2015.

Salguero-Olvera, C.A. (2018). Análisis del impacto del agua subterránea en el régimen de caudal ambiental en el Río Grande de Comitán, Chiapas [Analysis of the impact of groundwater on the environmental flow regime in the Río Grande de Comitán, Chiapas] (Master's thesis). Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, México.